

Application of Ultra-Rapid Reactivity (UR²) Test for at-line Characterization of Calcined Clay Reactivity

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Abstract. Clay calcination is an industrial process used to produce a reactive supplementary cementitious material (SCMs), calcined clay – which is a partial clinker replacement in cement. Despite the well-documented reactivity of calcined clays, existing test methods such as R³ test and Strength Activity Index (SAI) are time-intensive and, thus, impractical for rapid process control in industrial settings. This prohibits plant operation to take immediate action to ensure the minimum targeted reactivity is reached at all times, resulting in: a) increased OpEx and CO₂ emissions since the potential partial clay substitution in cement ought to be reduced or, in the worst case, rejected and production lost; and/or b) larger storage facilities at high CapEx due to the longer response time to the ensure the material quality is confirmed. To address this challenge, a 5-minute Ultra-Rapid Reactivity (UR²) test was recently proposed. To assess the UR² feasibility as an at-line control tool, a natural clay was calcined in a pilot-scale flash calciner across temperatures of 825 to 925°C under oxidizing and reducing conditions. Also, the clay was calcined at laboratory scale, extending the temperature range down to 550°C. All samples were assessed by UR² and SAI; with a subset evaluated using R³. The UR² showed a strong correlation with R³ and SAI across all calcination temperatures. This trend was sustained when data from laboratory and pilot scale are evaluated together – including samples with maximum particle size ranging from 45 to 90 μm – showcasing the robustness of the UR² to capture clay reactivity. Overall, our findings support the application of the 5-minute UR² as a rapid screening method for assessing calcined clay reactivity and its integration into industrial settings – upon controlled sample preparation – for at-line monitoring and evaluation of clay suitability, prior to full-scale calcination trials.

Keywords: calcined clay; calcination; reactivity; rapid characterization

1 Introduction

SCMs reactivity is critical to their performance as a clinker replacement. Various methods based on different principles of reactivity are employed to assess reactivity [1] in model (synthetic) or cementitious systems under normal and accelerated conditions. The rate of reactivity is primarily assessed by evaluating key properties of the reaction, e.g. a) portlandite consumption (Chapelle test [2], Frattini test [3]) and b) degree of

SCM reaction inferred from bound water quantity and heat released during the reaction (R^3 test [4]), among other properties. While these properties are widely examined, they come with specific limitations, e.g. portlandite consumption may result from carbonation, and does not accurately reflect hydraulic SCMs reactivity. Next, assessing the degree of reaction often requires destructive testing and is limited by indirect measurements. Bound water content is also influenced by multiple hydration reactions and is sensitive to curing conditions, limiting its specificity. Similarly, heat evolution may not accurately reflect the reactivity of slowly reacting SCMs.

Although notable advancements in reactivity testing have been made in recent decades, e.g. R^3 Test [4], a major limitation of current methods is the excessive time required for testing and evaluation (1 to 28 days). The extended testing periods fall short when it comes to providing quick feedback, which is crucial for large-scale industry applications. Also, the long durations of traditional methods, combined with the inherent variability in the SCMs composition, hinder their adoption and integration into blended cements that rely on at-line characterization. Besides, some reactivity tests require advanced experimental setups, which may not be readily available in all production facilities. At present, the fastest method accepted in industry for measuring reactivity of calcined clays and correlating it to the composite cement strength is the R^3 test.

Figure 1. Industrial flash calcination unit: (a) working principles and (b) pilot-scale plant [6].

To address the prolonged turnaround time associated with existing reactivity tests, a 5-minute Ultra-Rapid Reactivity (UR^2) test was recently proposed [5]. To evaluate the UR^2 feasibility as an at-line control tool, a natural clay was calcined in a pilot-scale flash calciner. Specifically, Figure 1 depicts the industrial flash calcination system as well as the pilot flash calciner at Fuller Technologies. Before calcination the material is processed in a dryer-crusher to get the required fineness and reduce clay moisture content. Next, the material is fed to the preheater/calciner system and undergoes thermal changes by dehydroxylation, to mention a few. Then, a cyclone at the outlet of the calciner separates the material from gas. The calcined clay is then transported to a

reduction vessel where fuel is injected if the calcined clay color is off specification. The clay mineralogy and controlled reduction environment determines the final product color from yellow/red enabling it to convert to grey. After that, the material undergoes a series of quench cooling cyclones for color preservation, heat recuperation and product cooling, so the final calcined clay product is ready [6].

Large-scale calcination tests are costly, driving the need to reduce time and cost associated with pilot-scale testing necessary to optimize clay calcination process parameters efficiently before full-scale industrial deployment. Hence, the main objective of this study is to evaluate the UR² test feasibility as an at-line quality control tool for assessing the reactivity of calcined clays in industrial calcination. For that, this study examines the reactivity of a natural clay calcined under laboratory and pilot scale operated at industrial configuration and conditions to establish the correlation between UR², R³, and SAI test for clays calcined used in the composite cement systems.

2 Materials and methods

In this study, a natural clay was calcined in the pilot-scale flash calciner (Fig. 1b) across a temperature range of 825 to 925°C under oxidizing and reducing conditions as well as in an electric muffle furnace. These samples are labelled as: C_s – soak calcination in a muffle furnace, C_o – flash calcination under oxidizing conditions, and C_r – flash calcination under reducing conditions.

The chemical oxide composition of the raw clay was determined via X-ray fluorescence (XRF) by the fused beads method; and the mineral composition by XRD using an Empyrean diffractometer from PANalytical, with CuK α ($\lambda=0.154$ nm). The raw clay samples were ground to ensure < 15% of the material was retained on the 90 μ m sieve, and TiO₂ was used as internal standard. Table 1 summarizes the XRF and XRD results.

Table 1. Elemental analysis and loss of ignition (LOI) determined by XRF, and XRD results.

XRF	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	TiO ₂	K ₂ O	Na ₂ O	LOI _{975°C}
	49.7	21.8	6.3	4.0	2.0	1.0	2.9	0.2	10.6
XRD	14% Quartz, 6% Dolomite, 7% Calcite, 27% kaolinite, 15% Mica.								

Thermal activation was carried out in two fashions:

- *Electric muffle furnace (C_s samples):* for this step, 50 ± 0.10 g of clay was placed in a quartz crucible, with an average powder depth of 1.0 cm. The raw clay was calcined at calcination temperatures (T_c) from 550 to 950°C for 1 hour. After calcination, the samples were cooled naturally and stored into sealed containers. The natural cooling for this clay has led to a water reabsorption < 0.5%.
- *Industrial flash calcination (C_r and C_o samples):* a raw feed of pre-processed natural clay in a dryer-crusher with 15% and 50% retained on a 500 μ m and 90 μ m sieve, respectively, was fed into the flash calciner pilot plant (Fig. 1b) and processed at a rate set at 80 kg clay/hour. The initial calcination temperature was set at 825°C and gradually increased to 925°C under oxidizing conditions. The material residence time in the calciner (Fig.1a) is between 1.2 to 1.3 seconds. Next, additional processing is carried out, i.e. after calcination the material enters the colour control unit

(Fig.1a) and is processed for an additional 1.0 minute in reducing conditions (C_r , if color controlled) and atmospheric conditions (C_o , if not color controlled) at a temperature that is approximately 25°C lower than that from the calciner, primarily due to process surface heat loss. For each material processing condition, calcined clay samples were collected when the system reached a steady-state temperature for at least 20 minutes. Next, a portion of the calcined materials (C_r and C_o) was ground to form two sets with different maximum particle size (ϕ_{max}), i.e. 90 and 45 μ m. These fractions, along with the soak calcined clay (C_s), were tested for reactivity using UR², R³, and 28d strength activity index (SAI) as described further in this section. Note that the clay feed is constant, thus, the tested clay reactivity is purely dependent on process, temperature, atmosphere and final ground particle size rather than clay feed particle size.

As for the material characterization the following tests were carried out:

- 7 days R³ Test (R³): The calcined clays' reactivity was assessed by the R³ test [4] – for a 7 days measurement. The samples were manually ground to ensure that the mass retained on the 45 μ m sieve was below 15%. Hence, the tests for the flash calcined samples (C_r and C_o with $\phi_{max} > 90\mu$ m) are not reported in the results section. The soak calcined samples (C_s) were tested since they are part of the exploratory work to evaluate the range of temperatures to be used in the pilot calcination plant.
- 5 minutes UR² Test (UR² index): Following the UR² procedure [5], calcined clay was dissolved in 4 M NaOH at 90°C at a solid liquid ratio of 0.5g/L. After 5 minutes the mixture was sampled and filtered. The filtrate was analysed for dissolved Al and Si by colorimetric UV-Vis measurements after the addition of standard reagents – the measurement (done in duplicates) takes about 1.0 second. Note that the total analytical time from sample received unprepared until results are ready (i.e. preparation, dissolution, and analysis time) is around 15 minutes. A dissolution index (1.54Al + Si) is calculated from the absorbance derived concentrations [5].
- 28 days Strength Activity Index (SAI): compressive strength tests on mortars produced based on EN196-1 [7] determined the SAI [8] at 28 days. A reference mortar (without clay) was prepared together with mortars where 20% calcined clay replaced the cement mass. The mortars were produced using a mass ratio of 1:0.25:3.75:0.5 (cement, calcined clay, sand, and water). The mixtures were cast into standard prisms, sealed with steel plate, demoulded after 24 hours, and cured at 20°C until testing (triplicate samples). For the calcined samples with $\phi_{max} < 90\mu$ m, the mortars were produced with CEM I 52.5N, while $\phi_{max} < 45\mu$ m with CEM I 42.5N. Hence, only the SAI and UR² data are used for a comparison of changes in reactivity between samples at different ϕ_{max} . The intent in testing calcined clays at different ϕ_{max} under the same processing technology is to evaluate whether changes in reactivity (i.e. released heat) and SAI (i.e. strength development in composite cement) due to grinding can be captured by the UR² test – similarly to what is known aspect for the R³ test.

3 Results and discussion

Table 2 summarizes all the tests results on the calcined clay samples, where UR_s^2 (-) and $f_{c,28d,s}$ (MPa) corresponds to the standard deviation values for each test.

Table 2. Reactivity tests results for all tested clay samples (Raw clay, C_s , C_r , C_o).

Sample	Calcination Process	\emptyset_{max} (μm)	T_c ($^{\circ}C$)	UR^2 (-)	UR_s^2 (-)	R^3 (J/g)	$f_{c, 28d}$ (MPa)	$f_{c, 28d, s}$ (MPa)	SAI ¹ (%)
<i>Raw clay</i>	-	< 90	-	995	221	-	-	-	-
<i>Cs-550</i>	Muffle furnace (Laboratory) Calcined in oxidizing conditions	< 90	550	1089	242	39	51.9	0.5	79
<i>Cs-650</i>			650	1620	361	138	54.3	1.9	82
<i>Cs-750</i>			750	2489	236	248	57.6	0.1	87
<i>Cs-850</i>			850	3039	104	282	58.7	0.6	89
<i>Cs-950</i>			950	2139	203	283	60.0	1.3	91
<i>Cr-825</i>	Flash calciner (Industrial)	< 90	825	2641	231	-	63.9	1.5	97
<i>Cr-850</i>			850	2438	503	-	64.1	1.7	97
<i>Cr-875</i>			875	2499	552	-	63.3	0.5	96
<i>Cr-900</i>			900	2402	228	-	65.9	1.0	100
<i>Cr-925</i>			925	1836	21	-	67.4	0.7	102
<i>Cr-825f</i>	Calcined in reducing conditions	< 45	825	4564	45	471	67.8	1.2	119
<i>Cr-850f</i>			850	4863	36	485	67.8	1.0	119
<i>Cr-875f</i>			875	4390	21	491	67.3	0.9	118
<i>Cr-900f</i>			900	4600	327	512	69.5	1.5	122
<i>Cr-925f</i>			925	4685	180	515	71.3	1.2	125
<i>Co-825</i>	Flash calciner (Industrial)	< 90	825	2414	69	-	60.0	1.5	91
<i>Co-850</i>			850	2612	42	-	61.4	0.1	93
<i>Co-875</i>			875	2774	320	-	63.9	0.1	97
<i>Co-900</i>			900	2675	38	-	63.3	0.2	96
<i>Co-925</i>			925	2486	244	-	64.0	0.2	97
<i>Co-825f</i>	Calcined in oxidizing conditions	< 45	825	4303	148	425	63.8	0.9	112
<i>Co-850f</i>			850	4186	116	451	65.0	0.7	114
<i>Co-875f</i>			875	4430	73	476	67.8	1.4	119
<i>Co-900f</i>			900	4438	44	486	67.3	1.2	118
<i>Co-925f</i>			925	4022	32	500	67.8	1.1	119

¹ For $\emptyset_{max} < 90\mu m$ - Reference mortar: 100% CEM I 52.5N; w/b = 0.50; $f_{c,28d} = 65.9$ MPa;
For $\emptyset_{max} < 45\mu m$ - Reference mortar: 100% CEM I 42.5N; w/b = 0.50; $f_{c,28d} = 57.0$ MPa.

Figure 2 depicts the correlation between R^3 and UR^2 results for clay samples calcined under oxidizing (C_s and C_o) conditions at lab and industrial scales – noting that the C_s samples were tested at particle size ($\phi_{max} < 90 \mu m$), as discussed in Section 2.

Figure 2. Correlation of 7-day R^3 cumulative heat and 5min- UR^2 index for clays calcined under oxidizing (C_s and C_o) conditions

The results from Fig. 2 show a clear increase in clay reactivity with rising calcination temperature (T_c) under oxidizing conditions, as indicated by both the R^3 and UR^2 values. The muffle furnace (C_s) samples exhibit systematically lower reactivity compared to the flash-calcined (C_o) clays, likely due to the coarser ϕ_{max} of the tested C_s samples rather than insufficient thermal changes caused by calcination. Similarly, the lower UR^2 reactivity of the flash-calcined samples (C_o) at $\phi_{max} < 90 \mu m$ compared to their fine counterpart at $\phi_{max} < 45 \mu m$ can be attributed to changes in particle size and increase in specific surface area (SSA); where finer particles are to exhibit faster reaction kinetics. Similarly to the R^3 protocol, this observation indicates the need to control the sample particle size for the UR^2 method. Complementary tests based on thermogravimetric analysis and SSA, to mention a few, are in progress and will help confirm this assessment; note that these are beyond the scope of this publication.

Besides, the strong linear correlation between UR^2 and R^3 ($R^2 = 0.94$) demonstrates that the UR^2 method effectively captures the associated reactivity across different calcination processes, thermal conditions, and particle sizes, validating its use as an indicator for assessing calcined clay performance and that the UR^2 test can capture a similar trend to that of the R^3 . Altogether, the UR^2 test offers a significant practical advantage, as it can be performed within minutes instead of days, providing an efficient tool for rapid screening of clay reactivity during early stages of product and process development.

From a calcined clay application outlook, Figure 3 depicts the correlation between R^3 and SAI for composite cement systems produced with calcined clays processed under all the tested conditions, i.e. reducing (C_r) and oxidizing (C_s and C_{of}).

Figure 3. Correlation of 7-day R^3 and 28-day SAI for composite cement systems produced with clays calcined under reducing (C_r) and oxidizing (C_s and C_{of}) conditions.

Figure 3 data show a strong correlation between the accumulated released heat (R^3) and the Strength Activity Index (SAI) for all clays, independent of the calcination atmosphere or process. This trend, consistent with observations reported in the literature [9], [10] confirms that both parameters capture the same underlying reactivity of calcined clays as pozzolanic materials in composite cements. The R^3 test effectively reflects changes in reactivity across different calcination routes, indicating its robustness as a comparative tool for calcined clay at laboratory scale as well as pilot scale flash calciner in industrial configuration and operating conditions.

Moreover, finer particles ($O_{max} < 45 \mu m$) exhibit notably higher R^3 and SAI values, highlighting the positive impact of particle size reduction on reactivity and supporting the practice of final grinding to enhance pozzolanic performance. Thus, the UR^2 method could be as a potential indicator to quantify the required calcined clay fineness to achieve a specific SAI in conjunction with cement or, if looking at the clay only, to quantify the required fineness to reach steady state reactivity of the calcined clay.

Complementary tests using different finer particle size distribution to determine the potential maximum reactivity are recommended. This is because erroneous conclusions on clay reactivity can be made if the test is not conducted at controlled particle size distribution from the reference industrial usage – unless correlation curves to particle size and reactivity are known. For that, the study carried out in [11] serves as a basis.

Finally, on the applicability of the UR^2 test method to capture changes in the reactivity calcined clays produced at pilot scale, Figure 4 depicts the correlation between

UR² Index and SAI for composite cement systems produced with clays calcined under all calcination conditions and sizes.

Figure 4. Correlation between 5min-UR² Index and SAI for composite cement systems produced with clays calcined under C_s, C_r, and C_o and sizes $\phi_{\max} < 90$ and $45\mu\text{m}$.

The correlation between the UR² Index and SAI across all calcination conditions and particle sizes (Fig. 4) demonstrates the UR² method can be used as an indicator of reactivity for a given material fineness. As such, the UR² test can be used to predict the reactivity of a clay as a function of customers quality control for a desired fineness to get the highest cement compressive strength. Alternatively, if the clay is ground to a standard maximum particle size, the UR² test can be used to predict the clay's reactivity resulting from a given activation processing condition. Note that the obtained results show that the boundary conditions related to the calcined clay particle sizes shall be established and that the tested clay shall be fine enough to ensure reactivity has reached a steady state, preventing an erroneous interpretation of the clay's reactivity.

The strong linear relationship ($R^2 = 0.92$) confirms that UR² captures variations in pozzolanic activity irrespective of calcination atmosphere and fineness, consistent with [5]. While the observed data scatter and 95 % confidence interval (Fig. 4) reflect minor experimental variability – likely due to sampling heterogeneity, dissolution kinetics, or measurement precision – these deviations remain within acceptable bounds for practical use and are to reduce when the comparing samples with a similar particle size only.

Importantly, the UR² test should not be viewed as a replacement for standardized R³ or SAI tests but rather as a complementary, at-line quality control tool capable of providing rapid feedback (within minutes) on product variability and process stability – upon a sample with controlled maximum particle size. To enable consistent industrial application, similarly to what has been featured in this publication, a calibration curve tailored to the specific clay source and calcination setup is recommended; such a curve

could also include the effect of particle size on reactivity so as to allow at-line tests without much work on sample preparation. Such calibration would allow UR² to serve as an efficient screening and process-adjustment method, ensuring real-time quality assurance while maintaining alignment with standardized reactivity benchmarks.

4 Conclusions

This study examined the reactivity of a natural clay calcined under both laboratory and pilot scale flash calcination to assess the applicability of the UR² test as an alternative to conventional reactivity methods. The results demonstrate a strong correlation between UR², R³, and SAI across all calcination routes and particle size fractions, proving its capability of capturing the effects of temperature, atmosphere, and fineness on clay activation and performance in composite cement.

Within the tested temperature range, the experimental results confirm that the reactivity of calcined clays increase systematically with calcination temperature, reflecting thermal changes of clay minerals, and variations in maximum particle size. The R³ and UR² indices consistently captured this trend and exhibited a strong correlation; thus, validating the UR²'s applicability as a proxy for traditional reactivity assessment. Similarly, the strong correlation observed between R³ and SAI, and UR² and SAI, confirm that both calorimetric and dissolution-based indicators reflect the performance of calcined clays in composite cement. Note that both the R³ and UR² specific reactivity is influenced by the sample maximum particle size; therefore, to predict and quantify the true potential reactivity of the calcined clays, it is recommended that the samples are ground to similar size as used in the intended cement product.

Altogether, the UR² method stands out as a rapid and reliable approach to assess calcined clay reactivity, providing at-line insights that can support conventional tests as well as plant operation and optimization. While deviations may arise from sampling heterogeneity, particle size, dissolution kinetics, or impurity effects, these can be mitigated through proper calibration against standardized benchmarks. This positions the UR² as a valuable quality control tool for both laboratory-scale development and industrial operations. Upon controlled sampling and preparation, the UR² enables early detection of variability and optimization of process conditions – i.e. it is suited for upcoming implementation in industrial plants.

Future research should focus on broadening the validation of the UR² test through interlaboratory studies and round-robin testing, exploring its applicability to clays of diverse mineralogical composition and maximum particle size, among others. In addition, UR² tests on clays tested at higher temperature operating conditions to the ones tested in this study will help confirm whether the UR² test captures the expected decline in reactivity when calcined clay recrystallisation occurs. Such efforts will help establish UR² as a reference method for rapid reactivity assessment and quality assurance in the production of calcined clay-based composite cements.

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